

Circular Fashion Revolution: Sustainable Fashion through Up-cycling and Traditional Textiles

Kiran Sharma*, Sambaditya Raj & Nitin Bhradwaj

Fashion Technology, Amity School of Fashion Technology, Amity University, Jaipur, Rajasthan

Abstract:

Background:

The fashion industry is under increasing pressure to adopt sustainable practices. Ranked as the second most polluting sector globally, after oil industry, the textile industry has a significant environmental impact. This situation has been exacerbated by the fast fashion phenomenon, which thrives on the constant creation, promotion, and disposal of trends over the last two decades.

Methods: *To highlight the wastefulness of the textile and clothing industry, we will briefly examine the adverse effects of fast fashion. Furthermore, we will investigate how the industry can shift from a linear economy to a circular one by incorporating traditional textiles and emphasizing reuse and recycling. Therefore, this research employed mixed method approach both qualitative and quantitative. It utilized convenience sampling to survey 50 fashion industry respondents and personal interviews with 5 key fashion stakeholders.*

Results: *The objective of this research is to examine and analyze the application of circular fashion principles through upcycling and traditional textiles, aiming to transform the fashion industry into a more sustainable and environmentally conscious sector. The results indicate that integrating circular fashion practices is vital for reducing the industry's environmental footprint and meeting the demand for sustainable consumer options.*

Conclusion: *Circular fashion aims to minimize waste and prolong the lifespan of products, with upcycling involving the repurposing of waste materials into new items. Traditional textiles not only offer cultural richness but also present opportunities for sustainability. Collaboration among stakeholders is vital for achieving long-term sustainability.*

Keywords: *Circular fashion, environmentally, sustainable practices, traditional textiles, up-cycling*

***Corresponding Author:**

Ms. Kiran Sharma

Research Scholar

Amity School of Fashion Technology,

Amity University,

Kant Kalwar, RIICO Industrial Area,

Jaipur – 303 002 Rajasthan

E-mail: ks04102017@gmail.com

1. Introduction

The fashion and textile sector stands out as one of the most environmentally harmful industries worldwide, largely because of its extensive production volume. Textile production demands vast amounts of land for cultivation and utilizes substantial quantities of water, energy, chemicals, and various resources. Regrettably, this frequently leads to unaddressed pollution, causing adverse effects on the environment, economy, and society. The fashion industry accounts for around 10 percent of total global carbon emissions and 20 percent of global wastewater. Additionally, it produces an alarming 92 million tons of textile waste annually, with projections indicating a potential increase of nearly 60 percent by 2030 if proactive measures are not implemented. Consequently, it is evident that the fashion industry is far from being environmentally friendly.

The current methods of clothing production have significant environmental consequences. The fashion industry thrives on creating, promoting, and discarding fashion trends [1]. In the past two decades, the pace of fashion has accelerated, giving rise to the concept of fast fashion. This phenomenon revolves around rapidly changing trends, excessive consumption, and low-quality garments that prompt consumers to purchase more frequently due to their affordability. However, these clothes are often discarded after just one season, exacerbating the issue of waste in the industry.

To combat the negative environmental impact caused by fast fashion, there are numerous solutions that can be implemented. This includes reducing water consumption, utilizing sustainable materials, and encouraging collaboration among various industries to promote a circular economy. Such an approach is essential for the textile and clothing industry to address the challenges it currently faces and to ensure its viability in an era of stringent environmental regulations. The goal is to maximize resource utilization while minimizing waste and emissions, all while maintaining profitability without harming the environment.

To highlight the wastefulness of the textile and clothing industry, this study will first assess the detrimental impacts of fast fashion. It will then investigate how the industry can transition from its current linear model to a circular economy by incorporating traditional textiles and emphasizing practices of reuse and recycling. The article will conclude with a thorough summary of the key issues addressed.

The primary objective of this study is to explore and analyse the implementation of circular fashion principles via upcycling and the use of traditional textiles, with the goal of transforming the fashion industry into a more sustainable and environmentally responsible sector. This research aims to understand how these practices can effectively reduce waste, preserve cultural heritage, and generate new economic opportunities, ultimately contributing to a more sustainable fashion ecosystem and fostering a circular economy.

1.1 State of clothing and textile industry

The textile industry is recognized as the second most polluting sector globally, following the oil industry. It is responsible for approximately 1.2 billion tons of greenhouse gas emissions, which exceed the combined emissions from international aviation and maritime shipping [2]. Projections indicate that by the year 2050, the fashion industry may account for as much as 25% of the world's carbon budget. In addition to these considerable carbon emissions, the industry contributes to ocean pollution through the release of microplastics [3]. The entire supply chain, encompassing the production and distribution of crops, fibers, and garments, results in air, water, and soil contamination. This situation emphasizes the critical concerns surrounding water consumption and pollution associated with textile wet processing operations, such as dyeing, finishing, and sizing. Consequently, these factors present significant challenges to sustainability within the industry [4].

1.2 Fast fashion

Recently, there has been a rise in "fast fashion," which refers to the production of cheap and trendy clothing that imitates high-end culture and celebrity ideas. These low-quality garments are sold at affordable prices, targeting low-income earners. Hence, fast fashion promotes mass consumption through low prices, but it also generates a significant amount of waste [5].

1.3 Circular Economy

The existing clothing system predominantly functions in a linear fashion, encompassing manufacturing, distribution, and consumption in a sequential manner. A substantial proportion of the fibers employed in garment production is sourced from non-renewable resources, particularly fossil fuels, which significantly contribute to environmental pollution. Typically, these garments are worn for a limited duration before being disposed of, either in landfills or through incineration. To effectively address these challenges, it is essential to transition from a linear economy to a circular economy. The circular economy is anchored by three fundamental principles: reduce, reuse, and recycle. These principles are intrinsically linked to traditional waste management strategies and aim to minimize waste, conserve resources, and promote sustainability within the fashion industry. (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Linear Economy Vs Circular Economy

1.4 Sustainable fashion

In the fashion industry, sustainability has become an increasingly important concern. One effective strategy to achieve sustainability involves the use of durable and long-lasting materials during the manufacturing process. However, this approach may not resonate with consumer preferences, as many individuals tend to replace their clothing according to seasonal trends and specific occasions. To effectively address the environmental impact of fast fashion and establish a competitive edge in a rapidly growing market, it is essential to embrace circular economy practices. These approaches aim to minimize the negative effects of the fashion industry on sustainability while promoting responsible consumption and production [6].

Therefore, here are a few examples of sustainable and eco-friendly approaches that can be implemented:

1.4.1 Sustainable and eco materials: Textiles are produced from renewable or sustainably cultivated raw materials that are non-toxic and free from pesticides. This emphasizes a preference for durable fibers such as linen, hemp, and bamboo.

1.4.2 Human rights: Numerous retailers have begun utilizing fair trade certification and membership as a means to demonstrate that equitable compensation has been provided to the producers of raw materials.

1.4.3 Environment friendly manufacturing: The garment industry has been compelled to adopt various eco labels and management systems, such as ISO Standards and OEKO-TEX, due to the combination of regulations, standards, and a growing consciousness regarding the use of less toxic and sustainable products

1.4.4 Local production: In order to mitigate the growing trend of globalization within the fashion sector and its subsequent social and environmental repercussions, manufacturers are shifting towards local production networks. This approach not only brings about various benefits but also enhances transparency and quality control throughout the supply chain.

1.4.5 Environment-friendly garment care: Numerous retailers are actively engaging with environmentally conscious consumers to deepen their understanding of harmful environmental effects linked to garment usage and maintenance.

1.5 Indian traditional textiles and sustainable fashion

India possesses a profound historical legacy in the use of traditional textile garments and techniques, such as handloom weaving and natural dyeing. These practices are not only environmentally sustainable but also exert a significantly reduced impact on the ecosystem when contrasted with industrial methods. As a result, the rich variety of traditional textile garments and techniques from various Indian states can be harnessed to transform worn garments into innovative new products through effective recycling and upcycling methods. Embracing these practices not only preserves cultural heritage but also contributes to a more sustainable future.

The textile and clothing industry in India reflects a rich tapestry of improvisation, philosophy, artisanal skills, and a shared commitment to optimizing limited resources. Recycling and upcycling handmade garments are deeply embedded in India's heritage, making substantial contributions to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions.

Each Indian state features its own unique textiles, characterized by distinct processes, designs, and patterns. Historically, these fabrics have been created using locally sourced materials, showcasing regional craftsmanship and sustainability. When transformed into garments, they were carefully tailored to cater to individuals of all ages and sometimes even passed down through generations. Moreover, these outfits were designed with consideration for the local climate. Notably, these garments were renowned for their long life-cycle, emphasizing reuse and recycling. Even after their initial purpose was fulfilled, they were creatively upcycled into practical items.

Aligning the sustainable techniques mentioned earlier with the traditional textiles of India involves recognizing the eco-friendly attributes deeply ingrained in India's textile legacy and combining them with modern sustainable principles. The subsequent details how each sustainable technique can be incorporated:

1.5.1 Sustainable and Environmentally Friendly Materials

1. Khadi: A fabric that is hand-spun and hand-woven, traditionally made from cotton but also from silk and wool, known for its durability and minimal environmental impact.
2. Organic Cotton: Grown without synthetic pesticides and fertilizers, commonly used in traditional Indian clothing.
3. Eri and Ahimsa Silk: Silk produced without harming silkworms, aiding in the conservation of biodiversity.

1.5.2 Human Rights

Craft Revival Initiatives: Projects focused on reviving traditional crafts often prioritize improving the livelihoods of artisans.

1.5.3 Eco-friendly Manufacturing of Traditional Indian Textiles

1.5.3.1 Organic/Natural Dyes

Traditional textiles frequently incorporate organic dyes sourced from plants, minerals, and insects, which are both non-toxic and biodegradable.

1.5.3.2 Artisanal Weaving

Weaving looms, which are manually operated tools employed to create a diverse array of designs and fabrics in various sizes, represent a tradition upheld by numerous communities throughout India. The hand-weaving process not only reduces energy consumption but also results in a low carbon footprint, thereby promoting sustainable manufacturing practices.

1.5.4 Local Production

Rural-Based Production: Many traditional textiles are crafted in rural areas, supporting local economies and preserving cultural heritage.

1.5.4.1 Local Markets

Selling textiles in nearby markets reduces the carbon footprint associated with transportation.

1.5.5 Environment friendly clothing care

1.5.5.1 Durable Fabrics

Khadi and handloom fabrics, known for their longevity, reduce the need for frequent replacements.

1.5.5.2 Simple Maintenance Tips

Many traditional textiles require easy, eco-friendly care methods such as hand washing and air drying.

1.6 Traditional Indian Textile Techniques

India has a wide array of traditional textile techniques that are used to recycle textile waste in different regions. Hence, traditional Indian textile techniques are instrumental in transforming textile waste into marketable products. As the population continues to grow, the issue of clothing waste has become increasingly significant. In various Indian states, numerous methods exist for repurposing old fabric and recycling textile waste, employing a range of surface embellishment techniques to produce innovative new products [7]. Some examples include:

Sujani embroidery, hailing from Bihar, showcases floral motifs on quilts, Panja dhurrie, or durrie, is a vibrant, flat-woven rug common in North India. Kasuti embroidery from Karnataka uses various stitches to depict nature and mythology, Patchwork creatively combines different fabrics promoting sustainability, Chakhlo represents traditional stuffed puppet art, contributing to India's rich textile heritage. These crafts highlight the skill of artisans and the importance of preserving cultural heritage.

To promote sustainable growth in the textile industry strategies like reducing, reusing and recycling are essential for transforming textile waste into valuable products. Traditional Indian crafts are vital in this effort as artisans skillfully repurpose used garments to create a variety of valuable items [8].

India's traditional textiles have gained global recognition for their outstanding quality. The Indian subcontinent is celebrated for its extensive artistic and cultural legacy. Historical records indicate that as far back as 2500 BCE, Indian crafts and textiles were exchanged with civilizations such as China, Mesopotamia and Egypt, originating from the Mohenjo-Daro and Harappan cultures. These textiles were produced using a variety of fabrics and techniques, including knitting, weaving, and decorative surface treatments. Methods like dyeing, printing, and embroidery enriched their visual appeal, incorporating designs inspired by the local environment, flora, and cultural elements. Preserving these traditional skills is crucial for sustaining the distinctive identity of local communities [9].

Textile recycling is crucial and important in ensuring the longevity of textiles. Improper disposal of textile materials can release harmful gases into the environment over many years. Recycling clothes provides a sustainable solution to this issue. There are various ways to repurpose and reuse recyclable clothing [10].

The materials utilized in the production of goods present five distinct methods for product recovery: repair, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing, and recycling [11]. As a result, artisanal products made from high-quality recycled materials enhance the longevity of the product [12].

1.7 Sustainable Craftsmanship: Upcycling Clothing into New Products

Upcycling, which involves giving an old, abandoned item a completely new life, is a fashion statement in and of itself. In India, the well-known adage "One man's trash is another man's treasure" is taken far too seriously.

1.7.1 Making Rugs and Quilts

Chindi rugs: Chindi rugs exemplify the innovative reuse of textile waste. Predominantly found in Maharashtra and Gujarat, these rugs are crafted by braiding or weaving strips of leftover fabric scraps, resulting in vibrant and multi-textured pieces. Renowned for their durability, Chindi rugs possess a distinctive character, ensuring that each rug is unique.

Ralli quilts: Typically seen adorning village beds in Sindh and Punjab, Ralli quilts are made by stitching together small patches of brightly colored fabric in a collage-like fashion. Various techniques, including patchwork, applique, and embroidery, are employed to create geometric patterns that frequently feature traditional motifs.

Kaithoon: Hailing from Rajasthan, Kaithoon is a traditional patchwork method primarily used to produce intricately designed quilts known as 'Gudri'. These quilts are made by sewing together fabric pieces, often sourced from old sarees and garments. Gudri quilts are cherished heirlooms, passed down through generations, encapsulating memories and cultural traditions within their fabric.

Pipli work: This brilliant appliqué method is used in Odissi artwork to create ornamental patterns by sewing colorful patches of fabric onto a base cloth. Wall hangings, canopies, traditional umbrellas, and even ceremonial decorations are frequently made using this technique. A significant cultural icon, pipli work is frequently shown at temples and at festivals. The cloth cover of the three chariots that the Puri temple's deities ride in each year during the Ratha Yatra is where the appliqué work is most noticeable.

Kantha: Kantha embroidery is a visible mending technique used in Bangladesh and West Bengal that entails piecing together worn-out textiles using straightforward running stitches. This method is frequently used to reinforce deteriorated fabric, extending the life of the garment. Women used to make quilts, bedspreads, and even clothes out of discarded sarees and dhotis by sewing them together and layering them. The simplicity of Kantha is what makes it so beautiful; the intricate patterns created by the repeated stitching give the fabric texture and vitality [13].

In order to produce several layers, homemakers recycle fabric waste and outdated fabrics to make quilts. Another technique for reusing textiles that makes use of clothing's adaptability is appliqué [14]. These methods and fabrics are extremely significant because they allow rural communities to express their culturally inspired images while also providing a source of revenue.

The obsolescence of fashion products is not solely due to material factors, but also influenced by shifts in consumer behavior and social dynamics. The future of India's textile and fashion industries will surely be impacted if recycling procedures for scrap fabric are not used in the industry, both on a small and large scale. Raising awareness among young textile craftsmen is essential to preserving and advancing traditional craft processes for future generations. This can be accomplished by highlighting the benefits of these methods and setting up training sessions and workshops, which will be assisted by the Indian government's textile ministry.

However, as the global sustainability movement picks up steam, contemporary Indian designers and companies are adopting upcycling more and more, drawing inspiration from old methods while creating new styles for the modern era. As a result, the Indian fashion industry has accepted the practice of recovering textile waste to prolong the life cycle of its products. In the current fashion scene below is India's conscientious brand reinventing upcycling in the following way:

Label Ka-Sha - At Label Ka-Sha- Fabric waste is repurposed at the source at Label Ka-Sha. During the cutting and stitching procedure, up to sixteen percent of the fabric can usually be thrown away. In order to address this, Ka-Sha started the "Heart to Haat" campaign, which recycles fabric waste into a range of goods, including as bags, macramé, stuffed animals, patchwork, shoes, and embroidery. To ensure that the least amount of trash is produced, the business also works with friends and other designers in the field to gather more leftover fabric.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Research objectives

The primary objective is to explore the potential of incorporating circular fashion principles, such as upcycling, reuse, and the utilization of traditional textiles, to promote sustainability and revolutionize the fashion sector.

- To investigate how traditional Indian garments and traditional textiles can contribute to circular fashion.
- To explore how the ethos of traditional crafts can slow down fast fashion and contribute to a sustainable fashion system.

- To assess the impact of integrating traditional knowledge on fashion and textiles into contemporary fashion design to achieve true sustainability.
- To evaluate the cultural tradition of extending the life span of clothing through reuse and repair in Indian customs.
- To investigate the prevailing beliefs regarding repurposing left over materials and its acknowledged significance for promoting sustainability.
- Analyse the shared awareness of the need to reduce pollutant burdens through waste reduction, reuse and recycling.

These objectives provide a structured framework for investigating the potential of integrating upcycling and traditional textiles into circular fashion to drive sustainability and transformation in the fashion industry.

2.3 Research methodology

This research study utilizes a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods. The secondary research involved a thorough examination of reports, books, research articles, and online sources to gather insights. Primary data collection consisted of a structured survey administered to 50 respondents from the fashion industry, followed by personal interviews with 5 key stakeholders.

2.4 Sampling method and sample size

This study employed purposive sampling to gather data. A total of 55 respondents from the fashion industry were selected, along with personal online interviews conducted with 5 fashion stakeholders. The sample of 55 comprised fashion faculty, designers, and fashion/textile students from Jaipur, ensuring that the participants had relevant knowledge and experience in sustainable fashion. This carefully chosen sample facilitated in-depth discussions, which enriched the insights necessary for understanding the complexities of the circular fashion movement within the broader context of sustainable fashion.

2.5 Ethical considerations and limitations

Ethical considerations such as informed consent, confidentiality, and adherence to ethical guidelines were taken into account throughout the research process. The study also recognizes limitations, such as the inability to study the entire population and time constraints.

3. Results and discussion

An online survey was conducted with 50 respondents and they were asked questions related to each of the four research objectives. The gender distribution is fairly balanced, with 52% females and 48% males, showing a slight female majority. This balance ensures that the results are not biased towards one gender, making them applicable to both male and female perspectives.

Figure 2: Gender

Figure 3: Traditional textiles or traditional couture existed long before the establishment of the fashion systems

A large majority (98%) of participants, with 38% and 60% either agreeing or strongly agreeing, believe that traditional textiles existed before modern fashion systems. This indicates a high level of awareness and acknowledgment of the historical roots and enduring nature of traditional textiles. A very small minority (2%) disagrees, showing almost universal recognition of this fact.

Figure 4: Traditional Indian garments such as the saris and the dhoties follow a zero waste pattern making principle. This is sustainable by design

All respondents (100%) either strongly agree or agree (54% and 46%) that traditional Indian garments like Saris and Dhotis follow a zero-waste design principle. This unanimous agreement highlights the strong connection perceived between traditional Indian clothing design and sustainable practices, emphasizing the importance and effectiveness of these traditional methods in sustainability.

Figure 5: Imbibing the true ethos of craft can become road map to slowing fast fashion

The vast majority (96%) of participants believe that embracing the authentic essence of traditional craftsmanship can help slow down the rapid pace of the fast fashion industry. This indicates strong support for traditional craft as a viable solution to combat the fast production cycles associated with fast fashion. The small dissenting fraction (4%) suggests some scepticism, although minimal.

Figure 6: Traditional textiles sector is eco-friendly and effectively deals with environmental sustainability

All respondents (100%) unanimously agree or strongly agree that the traditional textiles sector is environmentally friendly and effectively addresses sustainability issues. This consensus highlights the sector's perceived environmental benefits and its efficiency in tackling sustainability challenges.

Figure 7: Sustainable fashion can be truly created if traditional knowledge on fashion & textile is integrated into contemporary fashion

A significant majority (98%) of participants firmly believe that incorporating traditional wisdom into modern fashion can lead to genuinely sustainable fashion. This strong support indicates a desire to merge traditional and contemporary methods in order to achieve sustainability. A small percentage (2%) of strong disagreement suggests a minor level of opposition, possibly due to differing opinions on the practicality or importance of such integration.

Figure 8: It is part of the Indian lifestyle to prolong the life of Garment through Reuse and Repair

All participants (42% and 58%) strongly agree or agree that extending the lifespan of clothing through reuse and repair is a fundamental aspect of the Indian way of life. This showcases a strong cultural norm of sustainability in garment usage, highlighting a deeply ingrained tradition of maximizing the utility of apparel.

Figure 9: It is crucial to up cycle leftover yardage, fabric scraps, yarn, and other materials

The majority of respondents (76%) strongly believe or believe in the significance of upcycling leftover materials, emphasizing a widespread recognition of upcycling's role in sustainability. However, there is a noticeable minority (22% and 2%) who are either unsure or do not believe, indicating a need for further education and awareness.

Figure 10: Upcycling/recycling has highly beneficial effect on sustainable fashion

Every respondent (100%) concurs that upcycling/recycling greatly benefits sustainable fashion. This unanimous consensus highlights a widespread agreement on the positive influence of upcycling and recycling practices on the sustainability of the fashion sector.

Figure 11: Reduce Economic & Environment pollutant burden which has led to the awareness of reuse and recycling

All survey participants (54% and 46%) strongly agree and agree on the necessity to lessen economic and environmental burdens caused by pollutants through waste reduction, reuse, and recycling. This unanimous agreement underscores a collective awareness and recognition of the significance of these sustainable practices in reducing environmental impact.

Focus group interview was conducted with the objective of gathering perspectives from different individuals involved in the fashion industry regarding the incorporation of circular fashion practices, with a specific emphasis on upcycling and the utilization of traditional textiles to foster sustainability. The outcome of the focus group indicated a unanimous agreement that integrating circular fashion through upcycling and traditional textiles is not only feasible but also crucial for the industry's future. The participants demonstrated a shared dedication to advancing these practices and emphasized the need for ongoing discussions and cooperation among all stakeholders to facilitate the transition towards a more sustainable fashion industry.

Hence, Crafts, particularly textile crafts, have a higher likelihood of influencing the practical value of consumption among fashion consumers and establishing a positive emotional connection to the product. This emotional attachment leads to prolonged product lifespan through increased usage, thereby aligning consumption with sustainability. The narratives surrounding the origin, heritage, and handmade nature of the product further contribute to the consumer's emotional attachment. Additionally, consumers are aware that their purchase supports livelihood generation for others, enhancing their emotional connection. Craft, therefore, serves as a bridge between contemporary and traditional elements and offers sustainable solutions through slow fashion strategies.

Consequently, prioritizing the circularization of production and utilization processes is crucial in preserving our planet, its environment, and minimizing the depletion of natural resources caused by fast fashion and consumerism.

4. Conclusion

This study underscores the significant role of traditional Indian practices and circular fashion principles in promoting sustainability within the fashion sector. Consequently, the objectives of the emerging circular fashion model aim to shift the linear economy towards more sustainable frameworks. These objectives can be categorized into four key elements of the clothing system: (1) materials, (2) production, (3) usage, and (4) post-usage. The analysis suggests that traditional textiles possess lasting qualities that can support the slow fashion movement. The recycling and upcycling techniques historically utilized in various regions of India play a vital role in ensuring a sustainable future for the Indian textile industry. These practices not only extend the lifespan of products but also generate employment opportunities for millions. By embracing these methods, a clear pathway is established to steer the industry towards enhanced sustainability and environmental responsibility.

5. Acknowledgement

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor for his invaluable guidance and support throughout this research. I would also like to thank the fashion industry professionals and artisans who shared their knowledge and experiences. I hope that this work will inspire and contribute to the ongoing conversation about sustainable fashion practices.

References:

- [1] Fletcher, K. (2008). *Sustainable Fashion and Textiles: Design Journeys*. (p. 212). Earthscan/James & James.
- [2] Change NC (2018) The Price of fast fashion. *Nat Clim Chang* 8:1–1. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-017-0058-9>
- [3] Pandey K (2018) Fashion industry may use quarter of world's carbon budget by 2050. Available from <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/news/environment/fashion-industry-may-use-quarter-of-world-s-carbon-budget-by-2050-61183>. Accessed 01 Aug 2020
- [4] Chen, X., Memon, H.A., Wang, Y. *et al.* Circular Economy and Sustainability of the Clothing and Textile Industry. *Mater Circ Econ* 3, 12 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-021-00026-2>
- [5] Aus, R. (2011). *Trash to trend: Using upcycling in fashion design* [Unpublished doctoral dissertation]. Estonian Academy of Arts. <https://www.digar.ee/arhiiv/en/books/15357>
- [6] Saha K, Dey PK, Papagiannaki E (2021) Implementing circular economy in the textile and clothing industry. *Bus Strateg Environ* 30:1497–1530. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2670>

- [7] Singh S. Development of a Collection of Garments Inspired by the Hawa Mahal Historical Monument. *Tekstilec*. 2020; 63(3):185–194. <https://doi.org/10.14502/Tekstilec2020.63.185-19>
- [8] Jaitly R. *Tanabana: Handwoven and Handicraft Textiles of India*. Ahmedabad: Ministry of Textile of India, Government of India; 2007
- [9] Shafi M, Yin L, Yuan Y, Zoya. Revival of the traditional handicraft enterprising community in Pakistan. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*. 2020; 15 (4):477-507. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-07-2020-0129>
- [10] Domina T, Koch K. Consumer reuse and recycling of post-consumer textile waste. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*. 1999; 3(4):346-359. <https://doi.org/10.1108/eb022571>
- [11] Vaananen N, Vartiainen L, Kaipainen M, Pitkäniemi H, Pöllänen S. Understanding Finnish student craft teachers' conceptions of sustainability. *International Journal of Sustainability in Higher Education*. 2018; 19(5):963-986. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJSHE-11-2017-0200>
- [12] Sandvik IM, Stubbs W. Circular Fashion Supply Chain through Textile-To-Textile Recycling. *Journal of Fashion Marketing and Management*. 2019; 23(3):366-381. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jfmm-04-2018-0058>
- [13] Witzling M. Quilt Language: towards a poetics of quilting. *Women's History Review*. 2009; 18(4):619–637. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09612020903138351>
- [14] Goldsmith B, Jenkins L. *The Best-Ever Applique Sampler from Piece O' Cake Design*. Concord: C&T Publishing; 2013. 305 p.